

**Ballistic Performance of Kevlar – Shear Thickening Fluid
Composite:**

A Numerical Study

*A thesis submitted to
Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur
In partial fulfillment for the award of the degree*

of

**Master of Technology in Civil Engineering
With specialization in
Structural Engineering**

by

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April 2015

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that,

- a) The work contained in this report has been done by me under the guidance of my supervisor.
- b) The work has not been submitted to any other Institute for the award of any degree or diploma.
- c) I have conformed to the norms and guidelines given in the ethical code of conduct of the Institute.
- d) Wherever I have used materials (data, theoretical analysis, figures, and text) from other sources in this report, I have given them due credit by citing them in the text of the thesis and giving their details in the references. Further, I have taken permission from the owners of the sources, whenever necessary.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled, “**Ballistic Performance of Kevlar – Shear Thickening Fluid Composite: A Numerical Study**” is a bonafide record of authentic work carried out by **Noushad Bin Jamal M** under my supervision and guidance for the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of Master of Technology in Structural engineering in the department of civil engineering at the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur.

The results embodied in this thesis have not been submitted to any other University or Institute for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

A Numerical model for yarn level behavior of plain woven neat Kevlar KM2 fabric as well as shear thickening fluid(STF)- Kevlar KM2 composites subjected to high velocity projectile impact is presented. Experimental investigation results available in the open literatures and other documents are compiled to simulate the constitutive relations and interaction behavior between the yarns. Each yarn of plain woven fabric system is modeled using membrane element. This model is first validated for both single layer and multi-layer systems, with available experimental results reported in the literature. Secondly, fluid-solid composite structure is modeled using a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian approach. This proposed method for STF-Kevlar can be generalized to model fluid domain interacting with the fabric under high strain rate deformations.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Body armors are used to protect human torso against impact. Modern body armor falls in to two categories: hard body armor and soft body armor. Hard body armor is made of metal or ceramic plates. Soft body armor mainly consists of layers of fabrics made of high performance fibers. For soldiers in the battlefield, soft body armor is often plated with hard body armor in order to provide enough ballistic protection. Farjo and Miclau [1] studied the tissue wounding caused by ballistic impact. It was argued that the entry of a bullet into the human body produces a cavity in the tissue and causes great damage. Even though the penetration is prevented, there could be internal injury in human muscles or organs [2]. In spite of this, body armor plays an important role in life saving. Intensity of impact, angle of impact, weight of armor, projectile geometry is the various parameters that govern the design of armor. A coat of mail or metal armor was vitally important to the soldier in the ancient times. It covered the body of the soldier, protecting his torso and it left his hands free to use his weapons. But it was heavy, and hampered the movement, expensive to make.

This enforced a new standard in the design of armor even from the ancient times. Back to history, Alexander wore Linothorax [3], a type of body armor made by laminating together layers of linen at the Battle of Gaugamela in 331 B.C. The other key ingredient was glue, which was placed over various layers of linen. Indeed, the laminated layers functions like an ancient version of modern Kevlar armor. The development of high performance fibers made the modern flexible body armors possible. They are made with tightly woven multi layered fabrics. The most widely used polymeric fibers includes Para- Aramids and Ultra high molecular weight polyethylene

Kevlar, Twaron, Spectra, Dacron are the modern era Para-aramid synthetic fibers which possess high strength to weight ratio, enabling them to use in the ballistic applications. Among them, Kevlar is puncture and abrasion resistant, making it the best choice for hull rails and sharp seams. It has poor compressive properties. Human quest for high performance armor has continued to reach at a novel shear thickening fluid-fabric composite. At the beginning of 2000s, shear thickening fluids (STF) were thought to be used as armor material. Addition of colloidal shear thickening fluids to Kevlar fabrics has been shown to enhance the ballistic performance.

Shear thickening fluids are an example of non-Newtonian fluids in which viscosity increases to form a solid like behavior at high shear rates. After the recovery of stress, fluid returns to its initial fluid like behavior [4-11]. Two main theories have been proposed by researchers till date. Hoffman made an important study on micromechanical behavior of STF. He proposed that below a critical shear rate, particles in the suspension are in hexagonally packed order. Above the critical shear rate, particles aggregate and randomly packed. This is order to disorder transition causes shear thickening [12]. Another theory named Hydro-cluster theory was first introduced by Bardy with Stokesian dynamics simulations [13]. This theory was supported by neutron scattering, rheological and rheo-optical tests as well as computer simulations [14-17]. Hydro-cluster mechanism arises from particle interactions in the liquid suspension. Under the high level stress, particles have contacts each other. This effect yields an increase in the hydrodynamic forces. Then hydro-clustering emerges which is defined as aggregation of the particles with increased viscosity and jammed behavior of the fluid [16, 17].

However precise knowledge about the role of STF to ballistic resistance enhancements is unknown till date. Even though the physics behind energy dissipation in STF based armors are unknown, the effect of shear thickening in colloidal suspensions has been experimentally investigated by several researchers and hence it can be taken as a basis to investigate the performance of STF based fabric armors. A numerical study involving such effects may help to engineer the armor subjecting to high velocity impacts with known material parameters and contact models. Once the model is validated with known experimental observations, a large number of simulations can be done to examine possible improvements.

In this circumstance, requirement of multilayer modeling enforces to have optimized computational cost to performance methodology. A simplified and efficient numerical model is essential here which triumphs over existing models where 3D FE are used along with intricate material models such as orthotropic or transversely isotropic constitutive relations, leading to reduction in enormous computational cost.

1.1 Literature Survey

Numerical models are based on finite element code. As this method provides a more correct representation of the fabric (some numerical models enable fabric to be simulated at fiber level), a more precise simulation of ballistic impact can be achieved. Among the main numerical

works undertaken so far, four classes can be identified: the pin-jointed model, the 3D continuum finite element model, the unit-cell based model and the membrane/shell element based model in neat Kevlar fabric system. Since this is a classified work, detailed information is unavailable. But to achieve development of a numerical model for the same, available literatures are used to get material parameters, contact definitions, geometric aspects and experimental observations reported with spatial and temporal variations of displacements and energy during ballistic impact.

1.1.1 Pin-Jointed Models

This type of finite element model uses orthogonal pin-jointed bars to represent yarns. Roylance and Wang [18] used a network of interconnected fiber elements to simulate ballistic impact and suggested that the pin-jointed model leads to a good agreement with the transverse deformation observed in the experimental investigations with high speed camera. Shim *et al* [19] incorporated a three-element linear visco-elastic model into the model to capture the strain rate sensitivity of Twaron fibers. Prediction of the residual velocity and energy absorption in the model show good agreement with experimental data. Based on this work, Tan *et al* [20] incorporated yarn crimp effects into the numerical model based on two approaches. The first approach is to include the initial low modulus region of woven fabric subjected to tensile stretching in the visco-elastic constitutive behavior. The second approach is to reshape the yarn geometry into a zigzag manner. The second approach is found to give closer agreement with the experimental results. Billon and Robinson [21] compared the validity of a pin-jointed model and an analytical model and found that both models are useful in predicting the ballistic performance of fabric armor. While the pin-jointed model is capable of presenting the fabric response to ballistic impact but the factors such as fabric structure, yarn-yarn and layer-layer interactions are not taken into consideration.

1.1.2 Unit-Cell Based Model

Unit cell based approach is a meso-scale study of membrane response of fabric in a cell element. Gruzicic *et al* [22] proposed a unit-cell based model where frictional sliding losses are not explicitly considered. Explicit yarn level model and continuous domain model are then compared; both using shell element. Continuous surface model found to be computationally 2-3 times cheaper.

Shahkarami and Vaziri [23] simulated the woven fabric in three steps: (1) development of the biaxial behaviour of the unit-cell; (2) development of the in-plane shear response of the unit-cell; (3) development of the out-of-plane shear response. The resultant model is incorporated into a material subroutine, which can be readily used with finite element software. The out-of-plane shear modulus is suggested to be zero stating that there is little resistance against shear force at the yarn crossovers. For the in-plane shear modulus, it is believed that this parameter is not to be considered in the mechanism influencing fabric ballistic performance.

1.1.3 Three Dimensional Continuum Based Model

A continuum based model demonstrated by Duan et al [24] used a constitutive relation with orthotropic elastic constants and simple Coulomb friction interaction model observed to have large computational requirements. Coupled shell and membrane element based finite element model developed by Barauskas and Abraitene [25] for multi-layer fabric packages (MLFP) of plain-woven para-aramid Twaron yarns showed acceptable results for wave propagation and residual projectile velocities in comparison with full detailed finite element simulations.

Dennis [26] used solid elements for a layer level description of the target. The target in the simulation demonstrated by Sidney et al. [27] is modeled at the yarn level with solid elements but the number of elements in the yarn has been dramatically decreased to be able to perform simulations with full sized targets with multiple layers. A 3D Local-Global model presented by Rao et al [28] involve linear solid brick element at yarn level geometric representation. This approach did not consider inter-yarn, projectile-fabric friction effects which are experimentally observed to be dominant factors in stress wave propagation. Hence the post impact geometry of the numerical simulation observed to be not matching with the experimental results.

Continuum based models such as those developed by Taylor and Vinson [29] and Lim et al. [30] involve homogeneous, isotropic membrane elements and thus are convenient for multi-layer fabrics of realistic in-plane dimensions. However, they fail to analyze the inter-yarn interactions such as yarn unraveling or yarn-projectile interactions involved in the impact and penetration of the fabric. To incorporate the actual weave geometry and the effect of inter yarn

friction, attempts have been made to establish suitable FE model using solid, shell or pin jointed truss elements.

1.1.4 STF Based Model

The impregnation of shear thickening fluid (STF) into high-tenacity fabrics has drawn research attention, because it enhances the ballistic performance of fabrics without inducing loss of flexibility as well as reduced weight of the fabrics. It is reported by Bok-Won Lee and Chun-Gon Kim [31] that the performance enhancement provided by the STF is suspected to be due to the increased frictional interaction between yarns in impregnated fabrics. In order to explore the mechanism of this enhanced energy absorption, a computational analysis has been performed to consider the effect of STF impregnation on the ballistic performance of STF impregnated fabrics.

A meso-scale shell-based finite element model having orthotropic constitutive relations and modified dynamic friction as a function of relative velocity at the contact zone was developed to capture the effect of STF impregnation on the energy absorption mechanism of ballistic fabrics. The results plotted are in good agreement with experimental observations but not at the expected improvement level to have a flexible armor. Even though the modification of friction can capture viscous shear dissipation it cannot capture full hydrodynamic dissipation expected in the interface.

Several sandwich type models of STF based Kevlar KM2 multi layer fabric systems were subjected to ballistic impact test and reported by Wagner et al [32]. These systems cannot fully be modeled using a modified friction model as reported above. Hence a numerical approach leading to possibility of modeling STF based composite armors with different areal densities and number of fabric layers may be developed in the present study.

1.2 Scope & Objective of Present Study

The objective here at first is to model numerically, a suitable neat Kevlar fabric subjected to ballistic impact. Towards this, single layer membrane element model is developed at yarn level continuum, considering yarn crimping, inter yarn friction and projectile-fabric interaction and easy to determine material parameters. The developed fabric model is then validated at penetrating and non penetrating muzzle velocities, impacted by different projectiles. The same model is further validated for multi-layer fabric system subjected to projectile impact. Second objective is to numerically model

STF-Kevlar composites with different stacking sequences. Towards this, the developed Kevlar fabric Lagrangian model is coupled with discrete STF material in the Eulerian domain in a single simulation called Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian (CEL) analysis.

1.3 Organization of the Report

Chapter 1 narrates the introduction to this work describing what researchers have reported in the open literatures including motivation of the work and various numerical models available such as pin-jointed models, unit-cell based model, three dimensional continuum based model, STF based model and then describing the current scope of this work. Material properties describing geometric attributes of Kevlar®, properties of Kevlar KM-2 fabric, and properties of Shear Thickening Fluid are described in chapter 2. Chapter 3 starts with the description of proposed numerical modeling approach incorporating at first, neat Kevlar layer model using membrane element and then its validation for single layer neat Kevlar fabric model as well as multi layer neat Kevlar KM-2 fabric model. A further numerical investigation incorporating the effect of projectile geometry and effect of stacking orientation has been described in the same chapter. Secondly, STF based Kevlar KM-2 Model with Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian formulation explaining Fluid-Structure interface is described with different stacking and mirror image composite targets subjected to projectile impact. Chapter 4 represents the closure of works with conclusions based on current study and scope of future works. All the references are cited in chapter 5.

CHAPTER 2: MATERIAL PROPERTIES

2.1 Geometric Attributes Of Kevlar®

The style of Kevlar® fabric considered in the present study is K-706, which contains plain woven 600 Denier KM2 yarns. The yarn density of the fabric is 34 yarns per inch. Typically, each yarn consists of nearly 400 filaments each of diameter of 12 μ m and density of 1440 kg/m³. Schematic diagram of cross sections of the fabric in both the directions (warp and fill) are shown in the Figure (1)

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of cross sections of the fabric

Table 1: Dimensions of the cross section and crimp of Kevlar KM-2 fabric (Jagan et al [33])

	2a (mm)	2b (mm)
Warp Yarn	0.75	0.11
Weft Yarn	0.63	0.12

2.2 Properties of Kevlar KM-2 Fabric

Impact event and its response by material are expected to be associated with strain rate dependency. But here in case of Kevlar it is relevant to state that the experimental observations by Cheng et al [38] wherein several uni-axial tensile tests at different strain rates up to 2500 /s shown to have no strain rate dependency. Strain rate independency has also been reported by Jagan et al [33]. In their experimentation it is shown that yarns are having a linear elastic behavior without undergoing significant plastic deformation. When stress reaches a threshold value, the yarn breaks suddenly, resembling a brittle type failure. Based on these observations, averaged values of quasi static experimental results, reported by Yu et al [34] as listed in table (2) for neat Kevlar KM2 Model K-706 600 denier, has been used to model the single layer neat Kevlar model subjected to impacts with a range of muzzle velocities.

Table 2: Uni-axial tensile test results of Kevlar KM -2 (Jagan et al [33])

Kevlar KM-2	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Ultimate stress(GPa)	Ultimate Strain at failure
Model K-706	82.6	0.15	2.929	0.004

2.3 Properties of Shear Thickening Fluid

Shear rate dependent viscosity plot, figure (2), of shear thickening fluid for volume fraction 0.57 (ϕ) reported by Wagner et al [32] is used to model constitutive behavior of STF. Density of the suspension is calculated based on general mixture rules. Wagner et al [32] reported that the silica particles used were having a density of 1.78 g/cc. Density of Ethylene glycole is 1.11 g/cc. According to mixture equation, for a volumetric fraction 0.57 (ϕ), calculated density for the STF is 1.492 g/cc. Material preparation and testing methodology has been reported in detail by Wagner et al [32].

Figure 2: Shear rate-viscosity plot of shear thickening fluid (Wagner et al [32])

CHAPTER 3: NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

3.1 Neat Kevlar Layer Model

Woven fabric has a multi-scale structure formed of elements ranging from micro-scale filaments to macro-scale fabric. As mentioned above, the full discretization involve in introducing solid yarn elements to computer modeling of the fabrics, however, dramatically increases the computational expense. In order to describe the composite effect on the woven fabrics, such models require modeling down to the level of individual yarns. In this study, a meso-scale membrane-based finite element model is developed to capture the energy absorption mechanism of ballistic fabrics. Abaqus 6.11 is used in all the numerical analysis. Each yarn is modeled discretely as a continuum and multiple yarns were combined to comprise the fabric. Abaqus element M4R is used as FE to mesh the geometry. Yarn material is approximated to isotropic in nature and this approximation avoids complicated testing methodology without deviating from the experimental observations on the fabric as well as yarn. The dimensions of the yarn are extracted from Jagan et al [33]. The cross section of a yarn interwoven into the fabric is modeled as shown in figure(1). Table (1) presents values of the geometric dimensions of the cross section and crimp obtained from measurements.

Figure 3: Numerical membrane element model for the fabric with spherical bullet

Figure (3) shows how the total fabric sample was modeled by using membrane elements of rectangular cross sections to represent the interwoven yarn comprising each fabric layer. By adopting membrane element to discretize the yarn, rotational degree of freedom is eliminated and only two translational degrees of freedoms are active, hence contribution of small bending stiffness by the yarn is neglected. This approximation reduces the computational cost without compromising the accuracy of parameters (Back-face deformation and residual velocity) under consideration. The fabric is modeled with a thickness of 0.23 mm and a yarn crimp wavelength of 1.548 mm. Figure(4) shows a numerical model using truss element reported by Jagan et al [33].

Figure 4: Numerical truss element model for fabric with spherical bullet

Membrane elements are used to mesh the yarn cross section so as to reasonably represent the cross-section profile. Each element follows linear elastic stress-strain behavior up to ultimate strength beyond which the element is assumed to be fully damaged and consequently removed from the system. A very small plastic strain is assumed to avoid spurious deformations and a fracture energy based criteria is used to define the damage. General contact algorithm is introduced between yarns at crossovers, and between the projectile and the fabric. All the contact tangential behaviors are modeled with simple Coulomb friction model. Unlike truss element model, membrane element model captures sinusoidal crimps in the yarns. Hence the un-crimp energy in the total strain energy is almost fully captured. A friction coefficient of 0.2 reported by

Jagan et al [33] after his experimentation in yarn pullout behavior is used to simulate frictional dissipation under relative tangential displacement. Fabric-to-fabric contacts were modeled with the same for multiple layered fabrics so as to be able to simulate the stress waves propagating through multiple fabrics from the impact point. The bullets are modeled as rigid bodies, using 3D solid elements.

3.1.1 Validation of single Layer Neat Kevlar Fabric model

First a numerical model of 7 inch by 7 inch single layer fabric fixed in 50.8 mm dia steel holder is simulated with same muzzle velocities reported by Yu et al. [34] and validated. Here the numerical model is subjected to three types of projectiles that were used in the experiment: (1) 0.22 CAL fragment-simulating projectile (FSP, 0.22 CAL, 1.1 g, MIL-P-46593A) as shown in figure (7) ; (2) stainless steel right circular cylinder (RCC, diameter = 5.51 mm, length = 5.50 mm, mass = 1.027 g, SS type 440C); and (3) stainless steel sphere (diameter = 5.56 mm, mass = 0.692 g, SS type 440C). Rigidly held condition as in experiments is simulated by considering all DOFs restricted from displacements. It can readily be seen from the figure (5) for spherical bullet that the numerical results after calibration of the model for with impact velocity are in very good agreement with their experimental counterpart.

Figure 5: Comparison of time histories of displacement at the impact point for spherical bullet

Even though the numerical simulation post peak displacement response history plotted in figure (6) and figure(8) for reference node of fabric under cylindrical projectile impact deviate a little, the peak and post peak maximum displacements are matching appreciably with the experimental observations

Figure 6: Comparison of time histories of displacement at the impact point for cylindrical bullet Fragment simulating projectile of 22 Cal. 1.1 g is modeled with the dimensional specifications shown below in figure (7)

Figure 7. Cross-sectional dimensions of FSP (G. Pageau et al [35])

Figure 8: Comparison of time histories of displacement at the impact point for FSP

Residual velocity of the projectile is the next major measure to be validated. Experimental observations of residual velocity reported by Yu et al [34] are used for the validation of numerical model. Residual velocities plotted in figure (9) shows an agreeable match with the experimental results. Hence the overall behavior of impact response of the fabric is captured with reasonable accuracy.

a) Spherical Projectile

b) Cylindrical Projectile

c) Fragment Simulating Projectile

Figure 9: Comparison of residual velocities

3.1.2 Multi Layer Neat Kevlar KM-2 Fabric Model

Single layer fabric system has been validated with the reported experimental observations. But this validation only helps us to confirm the material model, finite element used to mesh, geometry of the fabric and inter yarn interactions. Inter fabric interaction exists in multi layered fabric systems and hence which shall be numerically validated with the experimental observations. For this, in the second phase of numerical modeling, multi layer system of fabrics of neat Kevlar KM-2 of dimension 50.8 mm x 50.8 mm as experimented and reported by Wetzel et al [36] is simulated. The projectile used here is a NATO standard fragment simulation

projectile (FSP), consisting of a chisel-pointed metal cylinder of 1.1 grams (17 grains) and 0.56 cm diameter (22 caliber) as shown in figure (7). Ballistic experiments were performed with 5.08 cm × 5.08 cm targets and a clay witness was used to measure the depth of indentation and from that, energy absorbed was estimated.

Figure 10: Multi-Layer Fabric System of four layers

The numerical model as shown in figure (10) involve more than one number of plies stacked in same orientation. The material of yarn is considered to be linear elastic isotropic and a fracture energy based damage is defined to delete the failed elements. Simple coulomb's friction model is adopted here in this case also and same frictional coefficient of 0.2 as used in single layer model is adopted to define inter yarn and inter fabric friction. The numerical simulation results obtained for the same system of fabric layers are then compared with the experimental counterpart reported by Wetzel et al [36]. From the experiment, it is reported that all the impact events are non-penetrating. Table 3 shows the experimental and numerical results.

Table 3: Experimental and Numerical results for Energy absorption of multi layer Kevlar KM-2

Target No	No. of Kevlar Layers	Average Impact Velocity (m/s)	Impact Energy(J)	% Energy Absorbed-Wetzel et al [36]	Residual Velocity (m/s) -Numerical	% Energy Absorbed-Numerical
1	4	249.5	34.24	59.0%	157.8	60.0%
2	6	216.3	25.73	70.6%	122	68.2%
3	10	251.5	34.79	82.1%	114	79.5%
4	14	234.9	30.35	86.0%	89.08	85.6%

It can be clearly seen from table (3) that the numerical models with membrane element have excellent agreement with the experimental counterpart for energy absorptions. All these residual velocities obtained from the numerical models are non-penetrating.

3.1.3 Further Numerical Investigation

Absorption of impact energy of a projectile can be separated in to increment in strain energy of the fabric, frictional dissipation, damage dissipation, increment in kinetic energy of fabric as a whole as described by Rao et al [28]. If the entire energy of the projectile can be absorbed by these mechanisms, the projectile will come to rest. When the kinetic energy of the fabric is reverted to the projectile in reverse direction of impact after a zero momentum state to projectile, it bounces back., otherwise it gets penetrated fully through the fabric. The energy distribution and failure mechanisms are significantly influenced by various parameters such as projectile impact velocity, projectile geometry, inter yarn friction , inter fabric friction and stacking sequence in case of multilayered fabric system. For neat Kevlar fabric inter yarn friction and inter fabric friction can be considered as constant. Hence the effects of stacking sequence and projectile geometry are numerically investigated and reported in the succeeding sections.

3.1.3.1 Effect of Projectile Geometry

In order to investigate the effect of projectile geometry in energy absorption mechanism, single layer neat Kevlar square fabric of side 50.8 mm has been numerically modeled as shown in figure(11.a), and subjected to different projectile geometries. A non penetrating velocity of 80 m/s and a penetrating velocity of 250 m/s are considered as impact velocity (V_i) in this study. In all the simulations, inter yarn friction coefficient is considered to be 0.2. In order to uniquely determine the projectile geometric effect, bore radius of 2.55 mm and projectile volume of 69.456 mm^3 are kept constant and the dimensions are calculated. Spherical , Right circular cylinder, Cylindrical, conical and semi ellipsoidal shapes as shown in figure (11.b) were chosen to model the geometric effect of projectile on impact energy absorption. Fabric was meshed with Abaqus four noded membrane element M4R, considering isotropic material model at yarn level continuum. Brick elements C3D8R were used to mesh the projectile. All the four sides were fixed to set the boundary condition. A node at the impact point is considered as reference for all the deformation histories plotted for comparison.

a) Numerical model for clamped square fabric subjected to projectile impact

b) Different projectile geometries considered in numerical model

Figure 11: Clamped square single layer fabric subjected to different projectile impact.

Time history plots for displacement at fabric reference point (impact point) are shown in figure (12) for $V_i = 80$ m/s. As we can readily observe that the deformation of conical projectile is much more than that of other projectiles. This is due to the fact that the sharp nosed projectile can easily damage the fabric and penetrate through it. Even though the projectile penetrates through the fabric, it cannot fully pierce due to lower impact velocity. It is evident that the in-plane motion of yarns is restricted by adjacent yarns through friction and hence expected higher frictional dissipation. It is observed that in the case of flat ended projectile the penetration takes place mainly due to yarn breakage resembling plugging type failure. Whereas in the case of round ended projectile, initially the yarns immediately in contact with the projectile breaks and then the round nose pushes the broken yarn laterally to create room for penetration to occur. In both the cases, before breaking yarns undergo un-crimping and subsequent pullout which absorb significant portion of the impact energy. From blunt nose projectiles, we can see that semi ellipsoidal projectiles are more vulnerable to torso protection.

Figure 12: Time History of Impact Point Displacement for Non Penetrating Impact

(a)

(b)

Figure 13 : History of energy dissipation by friction

a) Non penetrating velocity $V_i=80$ m/s. b) Penetrating velocity $V_i = 250$ m/s

From figure (13.a) and figure (13.b) it is interesting to note that only the geometry doesn't describe frictional dissipation. At higher impact velocities RCC projectile allows more contact area with the yarns there by straining more number of yarns before allowing them to damage. But at lower velocities conical projectile causes the yarns to move in plane since it penetrates and there by mobilize more friction compared to other geometries. Here it is observed that the impact velocity is very much related to projectile geometry in frictional dissipation.

Figure 14: Bar chart showing geometric effect on residual velocity

Figure (14) show the residual velocities of projectiles in both penetrating and non penetrating velocities. One can observe that in the case of blunt nose projectiles, semi ellipsoidal projectile has least value of rebound velocity at $V_i=80$ m/s and highest value for residual velocity in case of penetrating range $V_i=250$ m/s. Hence this geometry can be considered as the better choice in manufacturing ammunicions.

3.1.3.2 Effect of Stacking Orientation

When the fabric is idealized to continuum membrane or shell, the stress contour can be observed with circular pattern concentric with the origin at the impact point. This particular pattern is an inherent property of the geometry, as the fabric is strained with considerable equality in radial direction from the impact point. But in the case of real single layer Kevlar fabric subjected to impact at the center, we can observe straining of yarns in a cross- like patterns and not in the radial direction. This peculiarity is the inherent nature of plain woven fabric. Multi-layered fabric system is the commonly adopted in soft body armor when single layer of fabric is insufficient to use at the expected threat level. Hence if it is possible to use the same number of plies of fabric with improved performance, it will be the best choice to reduce the weight of armor at the same threat level.

As discussed earlier, radial straining allows more number of yarns to participate in energy dissipation. This can be achieved by reorienting the fabric plies in each layer. Figure (15) shows an example for different stacking orientation for four layers of neat Kevlar fabric.

Figure 15: Four Layer Neat Kevlar fabric with skewed stacking subjected to FSP projectile impact

In this numerical model, to demonstrate the possibility of optimization of fabric in projectile impact at desired threat level, a four layer neat Kevlar fabric is considered. Plies of square size 50.8 mm are reoriented in each layer and subjected to 0.22 Cal FSP with an impact velocity of 250 m/s. All the four sides of fabric are fixed to define boundary condition. As an example to demonstrate the nature of deformation pattern, orientations of 0-0-0-0 and 0-0-45-45 are shown in figure (16) with their deformation contour.

Figure 16: Displacement contours of four layers of neat Kevlar with different stacking orientations at 30 micro seconds

We can clearly see that 0-0-0-0 orientation is having a diamond shaped contours of displacement and 0-0-45-45 is having a circular contour both originating from the impact point. From this observation, it is expected that the area of yarns strained will be more in case of 0-0-45-45 orientation, and hence can be expected with lower value for fabric back face signature(deformation) and higher energy dissipation at the same impact velocity.

Figure 17: Energy absorption for different stacking angles

Figure 18: Back face deformation of fabric at different stacking angles

When we observe the percentage dissipation for different stacking orientation as shown in figure (17) we can see that the best orientation is 0-0-45-45 which absorbs around 19% higher energy than conventional 0-0-0-0 orientation. This is really interesting to note that mere changing of orientation gives appreciable enhancement in energy absorption. But one should note that only the energy absorption is not good enough to define the suitability of armor, and the

maximum deformation possible at the desired threat level (muzzle velocity) is also a parameter which defines intensity of blunt trauma. From figure (18) it is observed that 0-30-60-0 orientation is having the least possible deformation and hence when displacement is considered as the criteria for armor, this stacking is the best choice for four layer system. When we consider both the energy absorption and back face maximum deformation as the criteria to estimate the required number of plies at considered threat level, 0-0-45-45 and 0-30-60-0 are the best choices to have better performance for four layers system.

Figure 19: Damage dissipation history of different stacking orientation

Performance enhancement by stacking orientation has a negative side that the material is considerably damaged at the impact point. From figure (13) one can see that the damage is more with skewed geometries and almost negligible in case of parallel stacking. It is very important to note this, as the same armor may be subjected to repeated impact. But one can continue with skewed stacking provided the damage is in control. When a composite panel is under impact, the projectile tends to exhibit through the thickness shear failure in the front layers, forming a plug;

for back layers the fiber damage resembles tensile failure [39-40]. Similar phenomena was observed by Chen et al [41] as well. Mixing different materials in a proper sequence would hopefully make the best use of their corresponding properties and consequently enable the ballistic panel to be more energy absorbing. When fabric damage is controlled, the best stacking sequence can be 0-0-45-45 in terms of overall performance for four layers of fabric system.

3.2 STF based Kevlar KM-2 Model

In the third phase of numerical investigation, the above neat Kevlar KM-2 multi layer fabric system is remodeled with inclusion of STF layer. Here, two kinds of STF-Kevlar are possible, a STF-Kevlar composite and impregnated STF-Kevlar. Both of them cannot be modeled with the same approach. Current numerical investigation involve only a STF-Kevlar composite where STF is filled in polyethylene zip-lock type bags and sandwiched between neat Kevlar layers.

Figure 20: Schematic representation of experimental setup for STF-Kevlar composite projectile impact testing

Figure (20) shows a schematic representation of experimental setup to test the ballistic performance of STF-Kevlar composite. Ballistic experiments conducted by Wagner et al [32] include similar arrangements as shown in figure (20). In the experiment done by Wagner et al [32], Kevlar KM-2 model 706 was used to sandwich polythene zip-lock pouches filled with nano silica based polyethylene glycole suspension. The sample was mounted on a wooden frame and kept on the target setup with a copper hoop. Spring holders were used to hold the target in front of a clay witness. In between the target and clay witness, a single layer neat Kevlar was used.

The arranged target was subjected to projectile impact with 0.22 cal FSP at an average impact velocity of 250 m/s.

Numerical model include a square fabric of 50.8 mm subjected to 0.22 cal FSP. Boundary condition of the model is defined with all sides fixity. Many problems are associated with the simulation of the above experiment. Among them, proper numerical solution approach is the main task. In this model, shear thickening fluid may be modeled in Lagrangian definition with Finite element approach. But the large deformation and erroneous definition of material failure restricts from using Finite element method. Further, solid (fabric and projectile) as well as fluid (STF) if defined in Eulerian approach will increase the computational cost and there by restrict the simulation for multi-layered systems. Hence, in the current approach, a coupled type of analysis is used where in solid is defined with Lagrangian approach and fluid is defined in Eulerian field. Interaction between them is enabled by the definition of penalty contact in which velocity component at interface normal to the surface is kept zero, viz, no two different material can occupy in single space, there by restricting penetration of two different materials with each other at the boundary. Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian approach in Abaqus 6.11 enables us to reduce the computational cost drastically and element deletion is suppressed for the fluid domain. A schematic representation of CEL analysis is shown in figure (21) and include the following major steps

Figure 21: Basic steps in Coupled Eulerian Lagrangian (CEL) Analysis.

1. Strain in element is transferred to each material in the element.

2. Each material is independently calculated for its stresses and other state data.
3. These data are combined using volume fraction data to find element averaged values.
4. Element Averaged stresses are integrated to obtain nodal forces

Impact on neat Kevlar with different projectiles has already been validated. Hence the same numerical FE model including material, damage and contact definitions will be adopted in CEL model to define the fabric and projectile. STF shall be modeled with proper estimation of stress while impact. A shock wave propagation model through compressible material is adopted to estimate the hydrostatic part of stress tensor and the same is derived in the following section.

3.2.1 Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian Formulation

The main concern in fluid-structure interaction problem in the computation of fluid forces that acts on the rigid or deformable structure. The computed fluid forces are applied on the structure as traction. In the fluid-structure coupling algorithm two superimposed meshes are considered, fixed Eulerian mesh of the fluid and deformable Lagrangian mesh of the structure.

3.2.1.1 Governing Equations in Eulerian Description

Consider a fluid domain $\Omega^f \in \mathbb{R}^3$ as shown in figure (22). Let $\delta\Omega^f$ represents its boundary defined by two boundary conditions, first, the boundary $\delta\Omega_1^f$ in which velocity is assumed to be specified as $v = g(t)$, and the second boundary $\delta\Omega_2^f$ where the tractions $h(t)$ are assumed to be imposed.

Figure 22: Schematic representation of fluid domain

In the Eulerian description, equations are written in spatial time derivatives and in standard Lagrangian description, material time derivative is used. The relation between material and spatial time derivative is related as follows.

$$\frac{D\phi}{Dt} = \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} + v \cdot (\nabla\phi) \quad (3.1)$$

Where,

ϕ - The arbitrary solution variable.

v - Material velocity.

$\frac{D\phi}{Dt}$ -Material time derivative.

$\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t}$ -Spatial time derivative.

Using the above relation, conservation equations of mass, momentum and energy defined in Lagrangian frame can be transferred with additional spatial derivative term to Eulerian description as follows.

$$\frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} + \rho(\nabla \cdot v) + v \cdot (\nabla\rho) = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + v \cdot (\nabla v) = \frac{1}{\rho}(\nabla \cdot \sigma) + b \quad (3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial t} + v \cdot (\nabla e) = \sigma : D \quad (3.4)$$

Where,

ρ - Mass density.

σ - Cauchy stress tensor.

b - Body Force.

e - Specific internal energy density.

D - Velocity gradient tensor.

The above equations (3.2) to (3.4) can be represented as follows,

$$\frac{\partial\rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho v) = 0 \quad (3.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial\rho v}{\partial t} + \nabla(\rho v \otimes v) = (\nabla \cdot \sigma) + \rho b \quad (3.6)$$

$$\frac{\partial e}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (ev) = \sigma : D \quad (3.7)$$

All the above three conservation equations (3.5) to (3.7) written in Eulerian description has the form,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (f) = C \quad (3.8)$$

$f(\phi, v, x, t)$ - In general, it is the flux function. x - Is the spatial coordinates and t - time. Operator splitting divides the above format (3.8) to two,

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = C \quad (3.9)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (f) = 0 \quad (3.10)$$

Where equation (3.9) is similar to standard governing equations in Lagrangian formulation and hence referred to as Lagrangian step and equation (3.10) is called Eulerian or Remap step where the convective term accounts for the transport of material between the elements. From the principle of virtual work, virtual displacement definition is used in Lagrangian step. In order to solve the equation (3.10), the deformed mesh in Lagrangian step is moved to Eulerian fixed mesh and volume of the material transported between the adjacent elements is calculated. In order to calculate the material occupancy in the Eulerian mesh, Element Volume Fraction (EVF) is defined. Initial volume fraction is referred to material volume fraction with fixed Eulerian mesh at initial state. Lagrangian solution variables such as mass, stress, energy are adjusted to account for the flow of material between the adjacent elements. Volume fraction information on the nodes is determined by the arithmetic mean of the EVF values of the cells surrounding the considered node. When EVF < 0.5 at a node, contact is not enforced on the fluid located at the node. The fluid can thus 'leak' into a Lagrangian body and so conservation of mass in the flow does not hold anymore. Taking a finer mesh decreases the amount of fluid that is lost due to leakage because the cells are smaller and quantity associated to each cell will be small.

Here Cauchy stress cannot be obtained at time $t+\Delta t$ by just adding Cauchy stress at time t with the incremental stress. This restriction is due to the fact that Cauchy stress tensor changes when the geometry including material is subjected to rigid body motion. Hence a second Piola-

Kirchoff stress tensor and Green-Lagrange strain tensor are used. Conservation of mass equation can be used in an integrated form rather than in its differential form (3.5) to have more accurate value. The integrated form is,

$$\rho J = \rho_0 \quad (3.11)$$

Where ρ_0 is the initial density or the reference density and J is the Jacobian defined by,

$$\det\left(\frac{\partial x_i}{\partial X_j}\right) = J \quad (3.12)$$

Operator split limits the maximum accuracy to second order. The Lagrangian formulation which is used in standard explicit finite element formulation is of second order accurate. Hence operator splitting will not be the actual limitation to the accuracy of calculation until third order accurate Lagrangian formulation replaces the current formulation.

3.2.1.2 Governing Equations in Lagrangian Description

Consider a structure domain $\Omega^s \in \mathbb{R}^3$ as shown in figure (23). Let $\delta\Omega^s$ represents its boundary defined by two boundary conditions, first, the boundary $\delta\Omega_1^s$ in which displacements are assumed to be specified as $d(t)$, and the second boundary $\delta\Omega_2^s$ where the tractions are assumed to be imposed.

Figure 23: Schematic representation of structure domain

Movement of the structure Ω^s can be described by $x_i(t)$ in terms of reference coordinates X_j where $i,j=1,2,3$. The momentum equation is given by,

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho} (\nabla \cdot \sigma) + b \quad (3.13)$$

Solution of the above equation satisfies the boundary conditions,

$$x(X,t)=d(t) \text{ on } \delta\Omega_1^s \quad (3.14)$$

If surface normal vector at $\delta\Omega_2^s$ is defined by n , the traction at $\delta\Omega_2^s$ is calculated as,

$$\sigma \cdot n = \tau \text{ on } \delta\Omega_2^s \quad (3.15)$$

3.2.1.3 Governing equations of Fluid-Structure Interface

Assuming Ω^s and Ω^f are in contact at the interfacial boundary and $\delta\Omega^c$ be the common boundary. If u is the gap normal to the common interface $\delta\Omega^c$ then the following condition must be satisfied at the boundary $\delta\Omega^c$ to establish contact,

$$u=0 \quad (3.16)$$

Two boundary conditions are imposed at $\delta\Omega^c$, impenetrability condition and traction condition at $\delta\Omega_2^c$. Since the boundary has no mass, traction condition is imposed by Newton's third law of motion as follows,

$$\sigma^s \cdot n^s + \sigma^f \cdot n^f = 0 \text{ on } \delta\Omega_2^c \quad (3.17)$$

Where n is the surface normal at the contact point. Using set theory, impenetrability condition can be represented as,

$$\Omega^f \cap \Omega^s = \{ \} \text{ on } \delta\Omega_2^c \quad (3.18)$$

If v^s and v^f are the velocities at the contact point where the surface normal n^s and n^f of solid and fluid are defined respectively, then in terms of penetration rate of two different bodies, expression (1.18) can be represented as,

$$\dot{u} = v^s \bullet n^s + v^f \bullet n^f = (v^s - v^f) \bullet n^s \leq 0 \quad (3.19)$$

$$\text{On } \delta\Omega_2^c$$

The condition (3.19) imposes a restriction that the fluid and structure should remain in contact ($\dot{u} = 0$) or remain separated ($\dot{u} < 0$). If a small penetration ($u > 0$) is allowed, equation (3.19) is violated. In this case a penalty approach is followed by applying an interface traction

force to establish the impenetrability condition. This force is applied to both master (Eulerian) and slave (structure) nodes in contact and scaled by shape functions.

$$F_s = -k.u \quad (3.20)$$

It is not clearly stated about the contact force estimate used in Abaqus 6.11. A good estimate of stiffness should reduce energy interface in order to conserve total energy and consequently prevent fluid leakage through the structure. In this explicit analysis, the following stiffness estimate can be adopted.

$$k = c_f * \frac{KA^2}{V} \quad (3.21)$$

Where, c_f - a scalar factor to avoid numerical instabilities, $0 \leq c_f \leq 1$.

K - Volumetric compressibility of the fluid.

A - Contact area of the structure node.

V - Volume of fluid associated to master node in contact.

If this estimate (3.20) for contact force is very large, then there is a possibility of separation of two surfaces. Hence to avoid this anomaly, a bound to contact force may be defined such as the one given by Belytschko and Neal [42] as stated below.

$$F \leq \frac{\frac{M^S M^f}{(M^S + M^f)}(v^S - v^f)}{\Delta t} \quad (3.22)$$

Where M is the mass associated to fluid and structure.

In an impact event, mesh deformation can very large and hence there is a chance to lose the fluid due to penetration with structure at the interface. The estimated stiffness may not be large enough to bring the material back to interface boundary in order to avoid fluid loss. Two remedies are possible, first to reduce the time increment and secondly, to define contact stiffness as a nonlinear function of penetration. Second approach to estimate suitable contact force is beyond the scope of current study.

3.2.2 Derivation Constitutive Model for STF

The most fundamental information about the shock wave propagation through any material is the equation of state derived from laws of conservation, viz, conservation of mass, conservation of momentum and conservation of energy. Suppose the material is filled in a non deformable cylinder of cross sectional area A with one end sealed and the other end connected with a rigid piston as shown in figure (24). Here, for the simplicity in derivation of the expression, unidirectional wave propagation. Initially the system is considered to be in equilibrated state.

Figure 24: Schematics of impact event with cylinder, piston arrangements

An impulse to the piston with a velocity U_p called particle velocity is applied at time $t=0$ (definition of impulse loading is considered here to set initial time equal to zero). Then the material at the interface of piston will begin to move with the same velocity U_p . This is acquired by a shock wave at the interface with a finite velocity $U_s > U_p$. The material to the rear face of this shock (entropy) will move with a velocity U_p but the material to the front of this shock will be at rest. Within the shock event, initial volume of $A \times U_s$ is converted to $A(U_s - U_p)$ there by changing the density from ρ_0 to ρ . From the law of conservation of mass,

$$A * U_s * \rho_0 = A * \rho * (U_s - U_p)$$

or, $\dot{m} = U_s * \rho_0 = \rho * (U_s - U_p)$ called mass flux. (3.23)

During this impact event, the pressure inside this system is changed from P_0 to P . Hence by the law of conservation of momentum, we can express,

$$m * \dot{U}_p = (\rho_0 * U_s * A) * U_p = (P - P_0) * A$$

Therefore, $P - P_0 = \rho_0 * U_s * U_p$ (3.24)

and the total energy of the system should also be conserved according to the law of conservation of energy. The applied impulse velocity having kinetic energy per unit time $\frac{1}{2} \dot{m} * U_p^2$ will

disturb the internal energy balance. This can be expressed in terms of change in internal energy density ($e - e_0$) per unit time as follows,

$$\frac{1}{2} \rho_0 * Us * A * Up^2 = \rho_0 * Us * A * (e - e_0)$$

$$P * Up = \rho_0 * Us * \left(\frac{1}{2} * Up^2 + e - e_0\right) \quad (3.25)$$

If we represent $Us = -u_0$ and $Us - Up = -u$, substituting this to equations 3.23 to 3.25 we get the following equations.

$$\rho u = \rho_0 u_0 \quad (3.26)$$

$$p + \rho u^2 = p_0 + \rho_0 u_0^2 \quad (3.27)$$

$$\frac{p}{\rho} + e + \frac{1}{2} u^2 = \frac{p_0}{\rho_0} + e_0 + \frac{1}{2} u_0^2 \quad (3.28)$$

The above three equations (3.26) to (3.28) are called Rankine-Hugoniot equations.

It should be understood that the pressure is used in place of stress in the indicated wave propagation direction. The key assumption in this derivation is that the shock wave propagation is steady. In this event, that shock state also called Hugoniot state, is achieved through a linear thermodynamic path called Rayleigh line. It has experimentally been recognized that the values of Us and Up can be related by a linear relation,

$$Us = C_0 + s * Up \quad (3.29)$$

Where C_0 - Wave velocity through the material at zero phase change which can be interpreted as the shock wave velocity at infinitesimally small particle velocity.

$$C_0 = \sqrt{K_s/\rho_0}$$

s - is the slope of linear Us - Up plot

K_s is the isentropic bulk modulus $K_s = -V * \frac{dP}{dV}$

By substitution of equation (3.29) to (3.27) and denoting shock pressure as Hugoniot pressure,

P_H

$$P_H = \rho_0 Up (C_0 + sUp) \quad (3.30)$$

From the equation (1.4) we can get

$$\frac{u_0}{\rho} = \frac{u}{\rho_0} \text{ or } 1 - \frac{\rho_0}{\rho} = \frac{Up}{Us} = \eta \text{ Combining this with the expression (3.30)}$$

$$P_H = \rho_0 C_0^2 \eta / (1 - s\eta)^2 \quad (3.31)$$

Shock induced pressure in solids are determined by Mie-Gruneisen equation of state relations which is a special case from Gruneisen equation of state model. Here it is assumed that

the same relations will be valid for shear thickening fluids where fluid to near solid phase transition is expected at high strain rates. The most common form is

$$P - P_H = \Gamma * \rho * (e_m - e_H) \quad (3.32)$$

$$\text{Where } \Gamma = \Gamma_0 * \frac{\rho_0}{\rho}$$

and Γ_0 – a material constant, e_m – specific internal energy at initial stage, e_H – specific internal energy at shock event

$$\text{The Hugoniot energy, } e_H = \frac{1}{2} * P_H * \left(\frac{1}{\rho_0} - \frac{1}{\rho} \right) \quad (3.33)$$

By eliminating Γ and e_H from the expressions (3.32) and (3.33)

$$P = P_H * \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma_0}{2} \eta \right) + \Gamma_0 * \rho_0 * e_m \quad (3.34)$$

Combining equation (3.31) and (3.34), pressure at impact event can be calculated as follows,

$$P = \frac{\rho_0 C_0^2 \eta}{(1 - s\eta)^2 \left(1 - \frac{\Gamma_0 \eta}{2} \right)} + \Gamma_0 \rho_0 e_m \quad (3.35)$$

There is a limiting compression, $\rho_{lim} = \frac{s\rho_0}{s-1}$

The deviatoric part of stress tensor can be calculated from instantaneous viscosity as

$$\mathbf{S} = \mu * \dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} \quad (3.36)$$

Where $\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}$ – deviatoric strain rate, μ – viscosity

Specific internal energy of the system before shock event can be considered as zero. Hence in expression (3.35), only the first term is considered. The same principle is used in current Abaqus model.

3.2.3 STF-Kevlar Numerical Model

An Eulerian domain is used to model the fluid STF. Figure (25) shows a numerical model for STF-Kevlar composite subjected to fragment simulation projectile impact under a muzzle velocity of 244 m/s.

Figure 25: Numerical model for STF-Kevlar composite subjected to fragment simulation projectile impact

Viscosity-Shear strain parameters are tabulated as input for numerical model after extracting the values of shear strain rate and viscosity from figure (2) for a volume fraction of 0.57 Silica in Ethylene glycol- nano silica suspension. Us-Up equation of state parameters are taken from the plate impact test results on shear thickening silica-ethylene glycol suspension, tabulated in PhD thesis report of Oren E Petel [37]. If no boundary is defined for the Eulerian element, during the analysis it can happen that the Eulerian material may go outside the Eulerian domain and consequently, the material is lost from the further analysis. In order to avoid material loss during the analysis, a zero normal velocity boundary condition is applied to the Eulerian domain. But one should be very careful that the Eulerian domain should be sufficiently large to accommodate the deformed Eulerian material throughout the analysis.

Figure 26: Schematic description of stacking for STF-Kevlar composite models

Three different stacking sequences were considered to study the model. Figure (26) shown here is a schematic representation of the composites under consideration. This study may help us to understand the effect of stacking sequence of STF-Kevlar composites in ballistic performance.

Figure 27: Percentage Energy Absorptions of Stacking sequences, A, B and C for different impact velocities

Percentage energy absorption for the considered stacking sequences A, B and C as shown in figure (26) above, has been plotted in figure (27). Here one can immediately notice that the energy absorption is getting decreased with the increase in impact velocity. This can be explained from figure (2) and figure (27). For a volumetric fraction of $\phi=0.57$, STF has an active range up to a shear rate of 1000 s^{-1} as shown in the figure (2). But shear rate history at the impact point is highly varying depending upon the impact velocity. From figure (28) one can observe that the shear rate goes above the active range of shear thickening or shear thinning of considered silica-ethylene glycole suspension. This reduces the effect of introduced STF in energy absorption.

Figure 28: Near field shear rate history for low and high velocity impacts

But at lower velocity impacts, the shear rate experienced at the yarn level is within the active zone of considered shear thickening fluid. This enables the performance enhancement of STF - Kevlar composites.

When different targets subjected to high velocity impact are considered, target A has got higher impact resistance. Reason for this can't fully be isolated to project the shear rate range experiencing during impact event. But as plotted in figure (29) one can observe that the shear rate varies spatially as well as temporally and hence in order to explain the performance improvement of STF-Kevlar composite, one should have shear rate information of that particular STF along with the information about the range of shear rate observed in numerical simulation or at best, from similar ballistic impact experiment.

Figure 29: Spatial and temporal variation of shear rate at low velocity impact

It has been numerically observed that the residual velocity of target A has got to 350 m/s approximately, after penetrating through the 8 ml STF layer for an impact velocity of $V_i = 400$ m/s. At the moment when projectile touches with the first layer of fabric, around 50 m/s velocity has been absorbed and four layers of Kevlar are further there active in absorbing the impact as shown in figure (30.a).

Figure 30: Instantaneous Residual velocity of projectile at high velocity impact. a) Target - A, b) Target B, c) Target C.

From figure (30.a) and figure (30.b) it can be seen that major part of the impact energy is absorbed by Kevlar only. But we can improve the performance of target by suitable choice of STF at the considered threat level.

3.2.4 Impact on Mirror Image Targets

Four layers 50.8 mm square fabric and 8 ml STF pouch has been sandwiched to form two mirror image targets A1 and A2 as shown in figure (31). These targets have been subjected to FSP 0.22 cal projectile with an impact velocity of 400 m/s to study the behavior of targets at direct impact to STF.

Figure 31: Schematic diagram of mirror image STF-Kevlar targets subjected to projectile impact

Percentage energy absorption has been plotted in figure (32). It has been observed from this numerical investigation that , if it is possible to stack STF-Kevlar in such a way that the residual velocity is brought down to a value by which the shear rate is within the range of active zone of STF, one can choose that as the best sequence of stacking.

Figure 32: Percentage energy absorption of mirror image STF-Kevlar composite targets

CHAPTER 4: CLOSURE

4.1 Conclusions

In this study an approach to numerically investigate fluid-fabric sandwich type composites subjected to ballistic impact has been demonstrated. In order to achieve this composite model, first a numerical fabric model is developed and then validated with reported experimental results for single layer plain woven Kevlar subjected to impact at center by different types of projectiles at both penetrating and non penetrating velocities. This Finite element model for fabric involves a membrane element meshing at yarn level. FEM involving membrane element is simpler and cheaper in computational cost, than some of the existing models with 3D solid and shell elements. Definitely, one dimensional truss element model is cheaper than the demonstrated one, but the fact that Truss element model gives an idea about global behavior of the fabric rather than how it interacts locally, especially when the fabric is in composite form with other materials such as shear thickening fluid. This yarn level continuum model has got another advantage that the material is considered to be homogeneous and isotropic, hence uni-axial tensile stress-strain curve is good enough to define constitutive behavior of yarn. Therefore, complicated experiments for determining material parameters of yarn when it is modeled as orthotropic or transversely isotropic material are not required. Geometry of the fabric model is in such a way that inherent yarn crimp effect is automatically captured. Further, parametric study on projectile geometry suggests that fabric is more vulnerable to resist impact by semi-ellipsoidal geometry from blunt nosed projectiles.

Secondly, this numerical approach is utilized to investigate multi-layer fabric system stacked in same orientation and subjected to ballistic impact by projectiles. Inter fabric interaction is defined with same penalty contact as that of inter-yarn interaction. Excellent agreement of numerical results with ballistic experimental results reported in referred literature validates inter-fabric interaction too. This multi-layer model approach is subjected to further studies with stacking orientation. Considering four layer system, a specific orientation setup has got near about 20% more energy absorption and reduced fabric deformation than conventional stacking. This points out that there a potential to study multi-layer fabric optimization using the developed numerical approach. Importance of including relatively soft and plastic thin layers between fabric plies is a remarkable observation from the extent of damage examined.

Finally, a coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian modeling approach is demonstrated using composites of Kevlar fabric and shear thickening fluid (STF) filled polymer bags, to model sandwich type fluid-fabric system. Difficulty in simulating large deformation using complete Lagrangian approach and computational cost involved in complete Eulerian analysis are efficiently resolved by this coupled simulation. The demonstrated fluid model can be applied to Newtonian as well as non-Newtonian fluids and hence it is a generalized way of modeling impact event in fluid. Parametric studies on stacking sequence and mirror image targets enlighten the possibility of developing light weight fluid-fabric composite systems. Most importantly, prior to experimental studies on these kinds of composites, selection of suitable STF can be easily made by investigating the range of shear rate experienced during impact event in the fabric at yarn level. Even though the proposed methodology has not yet been investigated with its experimental counterpart, it is expected that there a potential to use this approach in simulating ballistic experiments on fluid-fabric composites.

4.2 Future works

At this stage of numerical study, proper estimation of contact force between the fluid (STF) and solid (fabric) is required to proceed with the validation of the proposed model. Parametric study can be done to investigate the effects of stacking sequence and orientation, projectile nose geometry, different shear thickening fluids, temperature dependency etc with the proposed approach. An in depth experimental investigation such as Split-Hopkinson pressure bar test and shock Hugoniot plate impact test is a prerequisite to determine the equation of state data. This numerical approach can further be extended to investigate ballistic performance of low cost fabrics such as Ramie, provided the material parameters are consistent with the proposed model. Experimental investigation on multi layer fabric with different stacking orientation is required to establish numerically observed performance enhancement.

CHAPTER 5: REFERENCES

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